

PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING OF PRESCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: The article analyzes domestic and foreign sources on the topic of changes in the creative thinking of preschool teachers in their professional activities. Categorization was carried out that allowed us to formulate the 3 most common approaches among researchers and practicing teachers: working by solving problem situations; impact on environmental factors; creativity training. Conclusions on the current state of scientific research on this topic and the most effective methods in terms of organizing work with adults have been developed.

Keywords: creative thinking; problematic situations; learning environment; kindergarten teachers.

Introduction.

The development of effective approaches to the development of creative thinking and thinking of students of preschool education is an urgent task of the professional education system. On the one hand, a teacher's creative self-awareness at work is the best prevention of the so-called professional burnout, on the other hand, a teacher who is able to meaningfully put personally important tasks, invent history, and be surprised with a child one of the most important factors is the formation of creative thinking of children in the group.

Developing creative thinking by working with problem situations.

Research related to this approach can be roughly divided into two groups: work with professional situations and work with problem situations in abstract material. In the first case, the main hypothesis is that according to the results of the analysis and analysis led by the trainer, several problematic situations related to the interaction between children and adults in the educational process, the teacher forms such a professional position, which helps to recognize similar situations in the group's ordinary life and use their development potential. In the second case, we usually talk about mastering certain universal mental operations or strategies, such as the theory of inventive problem solving (TRIZ) or dialectical thinking operations. According to a number of researchers, it is necessary to transfer the new mental tools to the professional context according to the results of the lessons.

An example of the first type of research is Christina De Simon's "*problem-oriented learning: a framework for teachers' future professional problem-solving*".

This work examines the impact of problem-based learning on the professional problem-solving skills of future teachers. The participants of the study were future teachers who had to take an introductory course in educational psychology. Both groups were led by one teacher (*author*). The same reading materials and other resources were used. The experimental class was scheduled the day after the control class to minimize carryover effects.

Mechanisms.

Before the course, the participants were tested using a series of techniques to check their initial level of problem-solving skills. After the course, an experiment was conducted using the case "you are not in my group". In the second case, the participants of the control and experimental groups were offered the following:

- ✓ *assess feasibility;*
- ✓ *loyalty to the teacher's opinions and actions;*
- ✓ *identifying the problem; describe and justify your approach.*

Points were awarded for the following points:

- a) *create questions that the participants want to ask the teacher;*
- b) *identifying the problem;*
- c) *formulation of the problem;*
- d) *evaluation of the described solution;*
- e) *propose a solution;*
- f) *use literature to justify the solution;*
- g) *use other sources to justify solutions.*

Study situations.

Problem-based learning emphasizes that situations used should be reliable, relevant, and unspecified, meaning that there should be multiple ways of approaching a problem, as well as different responses. Interestingly, for developmental work, cases were offered for analysis to teachers who rated each case on a scale of 1 to 7. Work to be considered acceptable:

- ❖ *must be real (the teacher believes that it can happen or is a real event);*
- ❖ *must be undefined;*
- ❖ *require research (the problem requires information outside the text);*
- ❖ *matter (logical problem).*

Teaching.

In the problem-based learning class, the teacher gave mini-lectures on educational psychology and taught students to analyze classroom problems in small groups. Mini-lectures are usually given after students have discussed the issues they have. Later, a specialist in problem-based education conducts special seminars: discussing the case, moderating the dialogue, helping the group to create hypotheses, considering the problem from different points of view. The teacher then moves on to making predictions, using additional resources, creating questions, and forming broader implications. The class was then divided into 10 small groups, giving students the opportunity to provide feedback to each other as they discussed, analyzed, and solved the problem.

The control class analyzed the same cases: the teacher used them as an example of a concept in his lectures or brought them to the end of the lecture to give students the opportunity to practice applying knowledge. Students also worked in small groups and discussed cases, but did not use special tools.

Literature analysis.

Among the studies on such topics, A. K. Belolutsкая and O. A. Shiyan, the main unit of the analysis of problematic professional situations performed within the structural-dialectical approach are opposite pairs. It is also possible to note the work of A. V. Kaptsov and E. I. Kolesnikova "dialecticism and the relationship between the level of conflict resolution in the axiosphere of the person", where dialectic is considered as the cognitive style of the cognitive

system and the axiosphere of the person¹. The purpose of the work is to search for the relationship between the dialectical representation of reality and the degree of resolution of value conflicts in the axiosphere. Research has shown that, in most cases, the higher the level of representational dialectics, the more subjects adhere to values that are equal in importance, but opposite in content.

Also of interest is M. M. Kashapov's article "*Suprasitiveness of thinking as a source of realization of event-cognitive components of the subject at various stages of professionalization of psychologists.*"

Environment for teachers' creativity.

In the modern scientific and pedagogical space, the works that suggest changing various environmental factors for the development of the creative thinking of future pre-school education teachers are widely displayed. Thus, as a result of scientific research and literature analysis, based on observations and feedback from supervisors, it was determined that three main areas support student creativity:

- *student activity;*
- *physical environment;*
- *learning environment.*

The authors note that the tool is not for assessment, but rather for the teacher to obtain a list of guidelines for pedagogical reflection. It should be noted that the environment of partnership, friendship and support is mentioned by many authors as the main condition for opening creative potential. Analyzing the research on the topic, he points out that the problematic situation can be an effective tool for the development of creative thinking, taking into account a number of principles. These include the principle of systematicity (using the dialectical method). The principle of complementarity of actions of situational and suprasitive factors (determines the personal situation, acts as a situational modulator); preventive principle; the principle of multiplication (*a known object is evaluated from different points of view*); the principle of contextuality (*the professional maintains a holistic picture of activity without being distracted by momentary variables*). It also emphasizes the need to understand problems that activate cognitive activity and seek a synthetic solution to a problem to initiate creative thinking. Based on the studied principles and laws of development of creative thinking, the author creates a "*creative*" curriculum based on the use of conflicting situations to develop the thinking of experts.

In conclusion, it should be noted that all these approaches can be used equally in the vocational education system, because they do not contradict each other. In addition, the analytical description of these approaches can be recommended to be introduced into the educational programs of educational organizations, so that they can independently create conditions for opening the creative potential of future preschool education students.

¹ *Капцов А.В., Колесникова Е.И. Взаимосвязь репрезентаций диалектичности и степени разрешения противоречий в аксиосфере личности. // Вестник Самарской гуманитарной академии. Серия «Психология». 2013. № 1. С. 116–132.*

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